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Evaluation of the thermal performance of composite insulated panels with metallic skin through steady-state numerical analysis – Part 1

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Abstract. The energy performance of the buildings is a wide spreaded area on which many research is done nowadays. However, because of the relative new large scale interest on it, there still are subjects that have limited research data available. One of this topics is the thermal performance of composite insulated panels with metallic skin, usually a closure solution for industrial halls, production buildings, commercial buildings or even office buildings. Because of the mandatory request of the Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) in the European countries and in Romania as well, is highlighted that is a lack of informations regarding the thermal behaviour of this type of technical solution and also, synthetic working data for building energy auditors, as linear thermal transmission coefficients values (Ψ -values) for the usually constructive details that compose a regular industrial hall is missing. Therefore, this paper aims to provide an insight about the thermal behaviour of this type of solution, by offering results of Ψ -values for four different dimensions of sandwich panels, which represents appropriate data for a thermal bridges catalogue that may be used directly by the building energy auditors.

1. Introduction

Due to the high rise of CO₂ emissions at global level – figure 1, in the last years a high interest for the energy efficiency of the buildings exists, which is growing.

Figure 1. Global CO₂ emissions in the period 1965 - 2016 (based on statistical data from [1])

One of the measures taken at large scale in the European Union countries is the introduction of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs), whose role is to prepare the market, to increase the awareness, respectively to inform the occupants of the building of how the energy is consumed in the building, and also to build the energy profile of the country's built-up fund by centralizing EPCs results in the national data bases (as is the case in Romania, for example). However, at least as regarding Romania, the number of specialists who are doing this type of analysis is relatively small, and also the methodology of calculation is limited. Although, especially for residential buildings and for usually constructive details

there are many detailed studies [2], [3], [4] regarding the heat flux transfer under certain conditions and the impact of the thermal bridges that occurs on the thermal performance of the constructive detail, there are relative new technical envelope solutions for which thermotechnical scientific studies are limited [5], aspect which may have as effect that the energy performance certificate results to be inaccurate.

As regarding state of the art for the investigated subject in this paper, in order to reduce energy consumption, worldwide research is carried out in an integrated manner, starting from the physical and chemical properties of materials. Thus, in Greece, Mastrapostoli et al. [6] investigated sandwich panels on which fluorocarbon-based "cold" coatings were applied, reflecting solar radiation and rejecting solar gains at the opaque exterior surfaces of the building. After application by spraying, these materials reduce the temperature at the surface of the panel, also reducing the indoor temperature inside the hall or the energy requirement to maintain a constant temperature inside. For a temperate climate, these materials can be used in industrial halls that have high internal gains caused by the technological processes, with the intended effect during the summer to reduce the cooling demand of the building.

Another direction of research in this area is represented by the use of phase change materials (PCMs), used in wall panels to increase the energy storage capacity. An experiment conducted in Spain by Castellon et al. [7] studied the behaviour of microencapsulated phase change materials (Micronal BASF) in conventional sandwich panels made of metallic outer skin and injected polyurethane foam, in order to increase thermal inertia of panels, therefore to reduce energy demand in operation of buildings. The study has shown the possibility of increasing the thermal inertia of the panels by adding PCMs during the manufacture process of sandwich panels, with the possibility of improving the heat transfer behaviour by increasing thermal inertia of the panels.

Carbonari et al. [8] studied sandwich panels with an air layer between the PCM (encapsulated in rigid containers) and the metallic layer, and achieved energy behaviour similar to high thermal mass walls.

Regarding composite insulated panels with metallic skin, under the assumption that is not excluded that studies have been carried out, the author did not find research undertaken from a thermal performance point of view or thermotechnical studies related to this constructive solution, either at national or international level, highlighting the necessity of studies in this direction.

Nomenclature

T	temperature (K)	Φ_{2D}	bidimensional heat flux (W)
λ	thermal conductivity (W/m·K)	ΔT	temperature difference (K)
q	heat flux density (W/m ²)	δ	thickness (m)
Ψ	linear thermal transmission coefficient (W/m·K)	h	height (m)
χ	point thermal transmission coefficient (W/K)	L_i, L_e	dimension (interior / exterior) (m)
U	unidirectional thermal transmittance (W/m ² ·K)	S_i	area (interior overall dimensions) (m ²)
h_i ,	superficial heat transfer coefficient	R	unidirectional thermal resistance (m ² ·K/W)
h_e	(interior / exterior surface) (W/m ² ·K)	R'	corrected thermal resistance (m ² ·K/W)
L_{2D}	bidimensional thermal coupling coefficient (W/K)	r	the ratio of corrected thermal resistance to unidirectional thermal resistance (-)
$L_{2D,a}$	bidimensional thermal coupling coefficient calculated with EN ISO 10211: 2017 (W/K)		

2. Theoretical considerations

2.1. Theoretical considerations regarding steady-state bidimensional heat flux calculation through FEM analysis

In order to study the influence on the heat flux transfer of geometrical and material thermal bridges that occurs in several constructive details of composite thermal insulated panels with metallic skin, specific for walls and roofs of non-residential buildings, FEM steady-state numerical analysis is undertaken.

For the steady-state FEM analyzes, software THERM 7.2 was used, which is a freeware elaborated within University of California, Berkeley, funded by U.S. Department of Energy (DOE). In the undertaken study, the heat flux perturbation caused by the existence of thermal bridges, either caused by the geometry or by the material inhomogeneity, is numerically calculated for several common constructive details, which are currently representing the closures of an industrial hall.

The partial differential equation solved in this case is the Laplace type equation or the heat equation without internal heat sources in stationary regime:

$$\lambda \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) = 0 \quad (1)$$

In the mathematical model of the software is also used Fourier's law:

$$\mathbf{q} = -\lambda \cdot \text{grad } T \quad (2)$$

2.2. Numerical analysis conditions used for the constructive details

2.2.1. Geometry. All lengths were measured by reference to the total interior dimensional system. Geometrical 2D modeling of the analyzed details was performed in accordance with the requirements of EN ISO 10211: 2017 [9] The analyzed details were sectioned with adiabatic limits at $d_{\min} = 1$ m towards the position of the thermal bridge.

Regarding the details of the wall coupling with slab on the ground, the geometrical modeling was made considering the inferior limit of the model being located at 20 m below the ground level.

2.2.2. Material properties. Design values for the thermal conductivities of the materials used in the constructive details studied in this paper are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Properties of the used materials for different constructive elements

Building element	Used construction materials	λ (W/mK)	Reference source
Wall / Roof sandwich panels	Galvanized steel	58	[10]
	Rigid cellular polyurethane	0.038	[11]
	Rubber band	0.25	[12]
	Reinforced concrete	1.74	[10]
Slab on ground	Gravel	0.70	[10]
	Soil layer	2.00	[10]
	Extruded polystyrene	0.042	[10]
	PVC frame	0.17	[12]
4-16-4 window, without applied films	Float glass	1.00	[12]
	EPDM seal	0.25	[12]
	Silicagel (desiccant)	0.13	[12]
	Aluminum	160	[12]
	Rigid polyurethane (seal)	0.25	[12]

2.2.3. Boundary conditions. For the most of the analyzed details, Fourier type boundary condition is applied, which involves knowledge of the temperature of the fluid (air) that is surrounding the solid (the building element). Therefore, the analyzes are made by using $T_i = 20$ °C and $T_e = -18$ °C for the indoor air temperature, respectively for the outdoor air temperature. Fourier condition is obtained by using the

law of conserving the heat flux density, therefore for the surface limit of the element superficial heat transfer coefficients are used, with the values presented in table 2.

Table 2. Superficial heat transfer coefficient values

Superficial heat transfer coefficient type (W/m ² K)	Direction of thermal flow		
	Upward	Horizontally	Downward
h_i	10	8	6
h_e	24	24	24

2.3. Analytical relations for the calculation of heat transfer coefficients

The results obtained through numerical analysis are integrated in analytical calculation, in order to determine the linear thermal transmission coefficients values (Ψ -values), which regularly are used by building energy auditors in heat losses calculation, and which often are available in thermal bridges catalogues for many type of constructive details.

The analytical relations used in order to obtain linear thermal transmission coefficients values are those indicated in EN ISO 10211:2017 [9].

$$\Psi = L_{2D} - \sum_j U_j \quad (\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}) \quad (3)$$

As regarding the analysed details of the slab on ground, the used analytical relation is (4).

$$\Psi_g = L_{2D} - h_{\text{wall}} \cdot U_{\text{wall}} - L_{2D,a,\dots} \quad (\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}) \quad (4)$$

3. Thermal performance of common constructive details of composite insulated panels with metallic skin

The studied details include regular constructive details of the building envelope for walls and roof, the interaction between them, the interaction between window and wall, with a comprehensive model for the air cavities of the window frame and glass, the interaction between wall and ground, also with a comprehensive model for the slightly ventilated grooves with small cross section, which are constructively specific for the wall panel's joint with the slab on ground.

For each type of constructive detail, four different dimensions were analyzed, which cover the main regular dimensions usually found on the market. The analyzed details followed by the obtained results, both numerically and by using the above presented analytical relations are presented below.

3.1. Detail of wall panels joint to the corner

The geometry of the detail is shown in figure 2 and the results, as isothermal surfaces and synthetic values of linear thermal transfer coefficients, are shown in figure 3, respectively table 3.

Table 3. Linear thermal transmission coefficients for the wall panels joint detail to the corner

Detail identifier	$\delta_{\text{insulation}}$	Φ_{2D}	R	R'	L_i	Ψ
	(mm)	(W)	(m ² K/W)	(m ² K/W)	(m)	(W/mK)
Wall panel (left)	60	23.312	1.746	1.636	1.00	0.039
Wall panel (right)	60	24.881	1.746	1.533	1.00	0.080
Wall panel (left)	80	18.332	2.272	2.080	1.00	0.041
Wall panel (right)	80	19.868	2.272	1.920	1.00	0.081
Wall panel (left)	100	15.137	2.799	2.516	1.00	0.040
Wall panel (right)	100	16.611	2.799	2.292	1.00	0.079
Wall panel (left)	120	23.312	3.325	2.932	1.00	0.039
Wall panel (right)	120	24.881	3.325	2.640	1.00	0.080

Figure 2. Detail of geometric modelling wall panels joint to the corner

Figure 3. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.1

3.2. Details of wall panels horizontal joints

3.2.1. Detail of wall panels horizontal joint. Specifically to the composite panels with metallic skin are joints between wall panels, usually at a distance of 1.00 m, joints that can be horizontal or vertical. In figure 4 the geometric detail of a horizontal joint is shown and the simulation results are presented graphically in figure 5, respectively in numerical form in table 4.

Figure 4. Detail of geometric modelling joint between wall panels

Figure 5. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.2.1

Table 4. Linear thermal transmission coefficients for the horizontal joint detail between wall panels

Detail identifier	$\delta_{insulation}$ (mm)	Φ_{2D} (W)	R (m ² K/W)	R' (m ² K/W)	L _i (m)	Ψ (W/mK)
Wall panel (down)	60	22.45	1.746	1.693	1.00	0.018
Wall panel (up)	60	22.38	1.746	1.698	1.00	0.016
Wall panel (down)	80	17.17	2.272	2.213	1.00	0.012
Wall panel (up)	80	17.11	2.272	2.221	1.00	0.010
Wall panel (down)	100	14.11	2.799	2.693	1.00	0.014

Wall panel (up)	100	14.05	2.799	2.705	1.00	0.012
Wall panel (down)	120	12.03	3.325	3.160	1.00	0.016
Wall panel (up)	120	11.98	3.325	3.173	1.00	0.014

3.2.2. *Detail of wall panels horizontal joint – hidden connection.* For the "hidden" area an equivalent thermal conductivity of the non-ventilated air cavity was calculated.

Figure 6. Detail of geometric modelling joint between wall panels

Figure 7. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.2.2

Table 5. Linear thermal transmission coefficients for the hidden horizontal joint between wall panels

Detail identifier	$\delta_{insulation}$ (mm)	Φ_{2D} (W)	R (m ² K/W)	R' (m ² K/W)	L_i (m)	Ψ (W/mK)
Wall panel (left)	80	17.52	2.272	2.169	1.00	0.021
Wall panel (right)	80	17.59	2.272	2.170	1.00	0.023

It is noticed that the results obtained for panels with a thickness of 80 mm have higher Ψ-values in relation to the first type of joint, but these values are also low. For other thicknesses of this type of joint, no other numerical simulations were made -due of the lack of technical details.

3.3. *Detail of wall panel wall joint with roof panel*

This detail represents the connection between a wall panel and a roof panel with a roof slope of min. 7°. The thermal section was simulated by using thermal insulation material with λ = 0.05 (W/mK).

Figure 8. Detail of geometric modelling joint between wall panel and roof panel

Figure 9. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.3

In table 6 it can be noticed that the values obtained for the linear thermal transfer coefficients are very low. For this type of constructive detail, the effect of geometric thermal bridge and material is almost inexistent.

Table 6. Linear thermal transmission coefficients for the joint between wall panel and roof panel

Detail identifier	$\delta_{\text{insulation}}$	Φ_{2D}	R	R'	L_i	Ψ
	(mm)	(W)	(m ² K/W)	(m ² K/W)	(m)	(W/mK)
Roof panel	60	22.74	1.721	1.697	1.00	0.009
Wall panel	60	22.34	1.746	1.737	1.00	0.003
Roof panel	80	17.74	2.247	2.175	1.00	0.011
Wall panel	80	17.24	2.272	2.250	1.00	0.004
Roof panel	100	14.37	2.774	2.685	1.00	0.013
Wall panel	100	14.06	2.799	2.759	1.00	0.005
Roof panel	120	12.17	3.300	3.171	1.00	0.015
Wall panel	120	11.89	3.325	3.263	1.00	0.006

3.4. Detail of wall panel joint with PVC window frame

The air cavities inside the PVC profile are considered as non-ventilated air cavities (figure 10). The simulation of this constructive detail reveals that Ψ -value related to the wall is relatively high and the influence of the thermal bridges on the wall panel increases with the increase of the thermal insulation thickness, as can be seen in table 7.

Figure 11. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.4**Table 7.** Linear thermal transmission coefficients for the joint between wall panel and window

Detail identifier	$\delta_{\text{insulation}}$	Φ_{2D}	ΔT	R	R'	L_i	Ψ
	(mm)	(W)	(K)	(m ² K/W)	(m ² K/W)	(m)	(W/mK)
Wall panel	60	25.66	38	1.746	1.340	1.00	0.157
Wall panel	80	21.30	38	2.272	1.614	1.00	0.162
Wall panel	100	18.60	38	2.799	1.849	1.00	0.166
Wall panel	120	16.77	38	3.325	2.051	1.00	0.169

3.5. Detail of wall panel joints with slab on ground

3.5.1. *Detail of wall panel joint with slab on ground – type 1.* It should be noted that all interstitial areas in this constructive detail with an inward or outward slot less than 10 mm were considered to be poorly ventilated air cavities (figure 12).

According to the obtained numerical and analytical results, it can be concluded that the joint of the wall panel with the slab on ground and the foundation beam, with a 10 cm overlap with the concrete slab and without the insulation of the base, is insufficient given the high Ψ -values obtained in table 8.

Figure 12. Detail of geometric modelling joint between wall panel and slab on ground

Figure 13. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.5.1

Table 8. Linear thermal transmission coefficients for wall panel joint with slab on ground – type 1

Detail identifier (-)	$\delta_{\text{insulation}}$ (mm)	Φ_{2D} (W)	ΔT (K)	L_{2D} (W/K)	h_w (m)	U_w (W/m ² K)	$L_{2D,a}$ (W/K)	Ψ_{detail} (W/mK)	Ψ (W/mK)
Wall panel	60	36.137	38	0.951	1.00	0.573	2.011	1.124	0.343
Slab on ground	--	106.104	38	2.792	-	-	2.011	1.124	0.781
Wall panel	80	31.600	38	0.832	1.00	0.440	2.011	1.142	0.364
Slab on ground	--	105.995	38	2.789	-	-	2.011	1.142	0.778
Wall panel	100	28.781	38	0.757	1.00	0.357	2.011	1.154	0.378
Slab on ground	--	105.931	38	2.788	-	-	2.011	1.154	0.776
Wall panel	120	26.861	38	0.707	1.00	0.301	2.011	1.163	0.388
Slab on ground	--	105.890	38	2.787	-	-	2.011	1.163	0.775

3.5.2. *Detail of wall panel joint with slab on ground – type 2.* For another type of detail, the thermal performance was evaluated with an overlap of the wall panel on the reinforced concrete element of 6 cm with a simpler type of fastening also – as can be seen in figure 14.

Figure 14. Detail of geometric modelling joint between wall panel and slab on ground

Figure 15. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.5.2

Table 9. Linear thermal transmission coefficients for wall panel joint with slab on ground – type 2

Detail identifier	$\delta_{\text{insulation}}$	Φ_{2D}	ΔT	L_{2D}	h_w	U_w	$L_{2D.a}$	Ψ_{detail}	ψ
(-)	(mm)	(W)	(K)	(W/K)	(m)	(W/m ² K)	(W/K)	(W/mK)	(W/mK)
Wall panel	60	30.624	38	0.806	1.00	0.573	2.002	1.134	0.233
Slab on ground	60	110.310	38	2.903	-	-	2.002	1.134	0.900
Wall panel	80	25.929	38	0.682	1.00	0.440	2.002	1.141	0.242
Slab on ground	80	110.248	38	2.901	-	-	2.002	1.141	0.899
Wall panel	100	23.022	38	0.606	1.00	0.357	2.002	1.146	0.249
Slab on ground	100	110.216	38	2.900	-	-	2.002	1.146	0.898
Wall panel	120	21.049	38	0.554	1.00	0.301	2.002	1.151	0.253
Slab on ground	120	110.195	38	2.900	-	-	2.002	1.151	0.897

Compared to the first studied model, by analysing results from table 9, an increase in the thermal flux for this type of detail is observed (with an increase of the linear thermal transfer coefficients related to the slab on ground, respectively a reduction of those related to the wall panels), suggesting the influence of the length of the overlapping of the panel on the reinforced concrete element. The same tendency, to increase the effect of the thermal bridge in the wall as the thickness of the thermal insulation in the panel increase is noticeable.

3.6. Detail of roof panel joint at ridge

In the assumption of ensuring the continuity of thermal insulation, applied in situ after the positioning of the panels at the projected slope – figure 16, it can be noticed in table 10 that the values of linear thermal transmission coefficients are negligible.

Figure 16. Detail of geometric modelling joint between roof panels at ridge

Figure 17. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.6

Table 10. Linear thermal transmission coefficients for roof panel joint at ridge

Detail identifier	$\delta_{\text{insulation}}$ (mm)	Φ_{2D} (W)	R (m ² K/W)	R' (m ² K/W)	L _i (m)	Ψ (W/mK)
Roof panel (left)	60	23.52	1.721	1.728	1.00	- 0.002
Roof panel (right)	60	23.52	1.721	1.728	1.00	- 0.002
Roof panel (left)	80	18.06	2.248	2.251	1.00	- 0.001
Roof panel (right)	80	18.06	2.248	2.251	1.00	- 0.001
Roof panel (left)	100	14.65	2.774	2.774	1.00	0.000
Roof panel (right)	100	14.65	2.774	2.774	1.00	0.000
Roof panel (left)	120	12.33	3.300	3.296	1.00	0.000
Roof panel (right)	120	12.33	3.300	3.296	1.00	0.000

3.7. Details of roof panels joints

3.7.1. Details of roof panels joint – type 1. Also specific to the composite insulated panels with metallic skin are joints between roof panels, usually at the distance of 1.00 m. In figure 18 is a type of detail of the geometrical modelling of the joint; the simulation results are presented graphically in figure 19, respectively in numerical form in table 11.

Figure 18. Detail of geometric modelling joint between roof panels

Figure 19. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.7.1

Table 11. Linear thermal transmission coefficients for joint detail between roof panels – type 1

Detail identifier	$\delta_{\text{insulation}}$ (mm)	Φ_{2D} (W)	R (m ² K/W)	R' (m ² K/W)	L _i (m)	Ψ (W/mK)
Roof panel (left)	60	21.88	1.738	1.733	1.00	0.002
Roof panel (right)	60	21.93	1.738	1.723	1.00	0.005
Roof panel (left)	80	16.81	2.264	2.245	1.00	0.002
Roof panel (right)	80	16.90	2.264	2.255	1.00	0.004
Roof panel (left)	100	13.65	2.791	2.779	1.00	0.002
Roof panel (right)	100	13.72	2.791	2.766	1.00	0.003

Roof panel (left)	120	11.50	3.317	3.297	1.00	0.002
Roof panel (right)	120	11.54	3.317	3.287	1.00	0.003

3.7.2. *Details of roof panels joint – type 2.* In the current practice, have been identified roof panels where the metal sheet is continuous in the joint area (see figure 20); thus such a detail of roof panels joint has been simulated. The results obtained are presented in figure 21, respectively in table 12.

Figure 20. Detail of geometric modelling joint between roof panels

Figure 21. Isothermal surfaces for detail 3.7.2

Table 12. Linear thermal transmission coefficients for joint detail between roof panels – type 2

Detail identifier	$\delta_{\text{insulation}}$	Φ_{2D}	R	R'	L_i	Ψ
	(mm)	(W)	(m ² K/W)	(m ² K/W)	(m)	(W/mK)
Roof panel (left)	60	29.45	1.738	1.287	1.00	0.201
Roof panel (right)	60	29.63	1.738	1.281	1.00	0.205
Roof panel (left)	80	23.68	2.264	1.602	1.00	0.182
Roof panel (right)	80	23.79	2.264	1.595	1.00	0.185
Roof panel (left)	100	19.99	2.791	1.897	1.00	0.168
Roof panel (right)	100	20.06	2.791	1.892	1.00	0.170
Roof panel (left)	120	17.39	3.317	2.181	1.00	0.157
Roof panel (right)	120	17.43	3.317	2.177	1.00	0.158

As regarding the analysed constructive details of wall panels, it is noticed that a low thermal performance is observed for the detail of the wall panel joint with the window and for the wall panel joint with the slab on ground.

As regarding roof panels regular constructive details, it is noticed that linear thermal transmittance coefficients (Ψ –values) are lowest than $\Psi \leq 0.015$ (W/mK), excepting the case when in the joint between roof panels the metal layer is continuous.

The effect of the analysed thermal bridges in Part 1 of the paper is further studied from the point of view of its occurrence; an additional analysis being made in Part 2 of the paper, for building elements (facades and roofs).

4. Conclusions

The results of this paper offers a comprehensive knowledge about the thermal performance of several constructive details using composite insulated panels with metallic skin.

Although that the constructive details for this type of technical envelope solution have a great diversity, already currently used in existent buildings, which is impossible to be covered, the results of numerical simulations presented in this paper provide an insight into the effect of linear thermal bridges that occurs, and also provides a working paper for building energy auditors, which are using linear thermal transmittance coefficients in the EPCs elaboration or in building energy audits.

The results may be applied directly in the evaluation of the energy performance for a range of non-residential buildings such as: conditioned industrial halls, commercial buildings, office buildings, etc. for which currently is used this type of building envelope solution. The results can be used as working data by building energy auditors and by civil engineering specialists, in order to obtain correct information regarding the energy consumption of the building during exploitation.

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